

Public Debt and Economic Growth in Tanzania: An Empirical Investigation

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Abstract

This paper sought to investigate empirically the impact of public debt on economic growth in Tanzania over a period of 1990 to 2023. Toward this objective, a Vector Error Correction Model and Johansen cointegration analysis were employed to test for causal relationships between the variables of interest, including real GDP, external and domestic debt, and external debt services. Being consistent with the Keynesian theory, the domestic debt found to positively affect real output and lasts for one year. However, the empirical results reveal a negative and significant long-run relationship between real GDP and external debts, as well as real GDP and external debt services, indicating that external debts and its services impair long-run economic growth. Findings support the crowding-out effect which results from external and rather than domestic debt. In line with the findings, this paper recommends to the government to pursue appropriate debt strategies and policies with the intention of improving economic growth. In addition, the study cautions the country against growing external debt to finance its increasing expenditure needs as this was found to have adverse effects on growth in the long-run. The implication is that government should be able to design policies to effectively utilize and manage the public debt by increasing productive activities and, hence, promote economic growth and development.

Keywords: *Public Debt, Economic Growth, External Debt, Domestic Debt, Vector Error Correction Model.*

JEL classification: *B22, B26*

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Introduction

Over the last five decades, most countries in the world have seen major development in their economies, Tanzania being included. The issue of the public debt has mostly been ignored by empirical research, despite the fact that it is the underlying key issue behind economic development in many developing countries. Investment in social welfare, education, health, infrastructure, and other sectors of the economies is very vital for sustainable economic growth and development. The high government spending associated with such public investments always make it difficult for states to fund them from tax revenues alone, and mostly leads to budget deficits of many nations (Chindengwike, 2021). Less Developing Countries (LDCs), faced with weak tax regimes and low per capita incomes, mostly choose public debt as the best option for financing government budget. It follows therefore; it is not surprising that public debt plays a particularly important role in developing countries. Public debt enables fiscal authorities to play their role in attaining economic stability and stimulate sustainable growth in the country (Manasseh *et al.*, 2022).

Public debt is one of the key macroeconomic indicators determining how a country is perceived in international markets. It is one of the factors that determine the flow of inward Foreign Direct

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Investment (FDI). In addition to that, given that states borrow primarily through the issuance of government securities, interest rates, the duration, and overall cost of debt financing have significant implications for the economy, and the provision of social services to current and future generations of country's citizens (Ndoricimpa, 2020). In order to be able to fill saving-gap public borrowing is an unavoidable and morally reprehensible for economic growth and development. Considering economic growth, external debt inject money from foreign investors into the economy, and internal debt are distributed among those who have more support than they can use and deficit spenders who lack enough funds for developing economic initiatives and other needs (Marobhe, 2018). Numerous empirical studies have been conducted overtime in order to determine the effect of public debt and economic growth in developed and developing countries.

The impact of public debt on economic growth is still a controversial issue among academicians and policymakers. Further analysis of this issue is necessary, particularly in individual countries to be able to extend our frontier of knowledge in the matter. Some studies supported the positive effect, while other researches proved the negative effect. Whereas, a third group proved the non-linear relation between them, which in particular implies the existence of a threshold level beyond which public debt negatively affects economic growth of a country (Makhoba *et al.*, 2022). Public debt is normally considered an essential policy instrument because it has a substantial impact on investment, employment, exchange rate, economic growth, and many other macroeconomic variables. Tanzania's persisting fiscal imbalances accompanied by the current rise in external debts emphasize the need to better understand the dynamics of public debts and their relation with key macroeconomic indicators (Taylor & Lokina, 2024). This paper adds to the literature concerning Tanzanian context for its public debt-economic growth nexus.

Study findings provide fundamental underpinning for effective fiscal policy and a successful strategy for debt management that ensures sustainable economic growth associated with improved social welfare. Empirical studies that analyzed the public debt-economic growth nexus in Tanzania are very limited in terms of approaches used. The main contribution in this paper is to disaggregate public debt into domestic and external debt and also factor in issue of external debt servicing into the analysis. The findings reveal the direction and magnitude of the effect of domestic and external debt on economic growth under the sampled period. Thus, policymakers can take these findings into consideration, in particular with the increased reliance on domestic and external borrowing to finance development projects in supplementing collected tax revenue. Utilizing the Vector Error Correction (VEC) approach is more appropriate since it normally overcome the problems associated with the traditional Ordinary Least Square (OLS) model.

Following the introduction, the rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews theoretical and empirical literatures, section 3 presents the methodology of the study, section 4 presents the empirical results, and section 5 presents the conclusion with some key policy implications and recommendations.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

In the literature of economic growth distinct relationships between public debt and economic growth have been proposed and discussed by various schools of thoughts. For the last few decades, the theories of public debt were centred on the contribution of debt management to the macroeconomic stabilization (Abubakar & Mamman, 2021). The concern was the possibility of constraints that fiscal policy might experience as a result of the structure and the size of the external and domestic public debt. Governments consider borrowing as an alternative for taxes, thus allows expenditure to increase without immediate changes in tax rates (Didia & Ayokunle, 2020). Three main theories will be briefly reviewed in this sub-section; Debt Overhang Theory, Dual-gap Analysis Theory and Keynesian Model.

Debt overhang theory

Public debt overhang is a situation in which a country's expected repayment ability on external debt falls below the contractual value of debt. Debt overhang has been developed as a result of the creation of a database concerning fiscal crises in recent years. Before the development of such data, it was not known that the balance of public debt affects economic growth of a country (Reinhart *et al.*, 2012). Considering few examples, Barro & Sala-i-Martin (1997) found that the ratio of government expenditure to GDP has a negative impact on per-capita GDP. However, it was not confirmed whether the amount of public debt has a significant impact or not. Meanwhile, Fischer (1991) found that a fiscal deficit has a negative impact on per-capita GDP, like wise did not confirm whether or not the amount of public debt affects per-capita GDP.

Up to a certain threshold, foreign debt accumulation can promote investment and growth, while beyond such a point the debt overhang will start adding negative pressure on investor's willingness to provide additional capital (Krugman, 1988). In the same vein, the growth model proposed by Aschauer (2000), in which public capital formation has a nonlinear effect on growth of the economy can be extended to cover the impact of public debt. Assuming that public debt is used at least partly to finance productive public investment, an increase in public debt would have positive effects to growth up to a certain threshold and negative effect beyond such threshold.

Dual-gap analysis theory

This is also known as two-gap theory which was developed by Chenery and Strout (1966) which states that, for undeveloped economy to attain some particular growth rate, there are two independent and separate constraints; saving gap and foreign exchange gap. These gaps will be filled up through the flow of foreign resources and a desirable targeted growth rate of economy will be attained. In the light of national income accounting principles, these two gaps remain equal in the export sense, but they are not equal in the ex-ante sense. Dual-gap analysis theory presents development as a function of investment and that such investment requires domestic savings, and if such savings is not sufficient enough to ensure that economic growth and development takes place then there must be the possibility of obtaining from abroad the amount that can be invested in a country which is identical with the amount that is saved. Savings is an important factor on which investment depends. Therefore, savings rate and capital-output ratio are two factors that determine development.

Keynesian model

Keynesian Model came about as a result of the Great Depression of 1930s. During this period it was observed that economy is not always at full employment. In other words, the economy can be below or above its potential. During the Great Depression, unemployment was very and associated with huge inflation, many businesses failed and the economy was operating at much less than its potential level (Keynes, 1936).

The Keynesian Model postulates that there is no real burden associated with public debt and it has no effect on growth of the economy (Uctum & Wickens, 2000). The real burden of a public debt occurs at the time when the government expenditure is made, that is, when real resources are being used up. Domestic public debt is basically debt we owe to ourselves and it does not add anything to our real resource base at any point in time. On other hand, external debt is different, it does add real resources to the economy, and those resources will have to be repaid in the future (Savvides, 1992). If public debt is being substituted for current taxation there will be an immediate macro-expansionary effect, an increase in public expenditure financed by a tax increase deity a different and lower multiplier than it does debt-financed public expenditure, in other words, public debt invokes no contractionary effects (Law *et al.*, 2021).

Empirical Literature Review

Sansa (2020) aiming to evaluate the impact of the public debt on economic growth and poverty during the period from 2000 to 2018 in Tanzania. The study employed the multiple linear regression model to

evaluate the impact of the public debt on economic growth and poverty. The study findings showed that there is a negative and insignificant relationship between the public debt and GDP as well as public debt poverty in Tanzania. The meaning is the public debt does not have an impact on the economic growth and poverty reduction during the period from 2000 to 2018 in Tanzania.

Hilton (2021) uses a dynamic multivariate autoregressive-distributed lag (ARDL) based Granger-causality model to test the causal relationships between public debt and economic growth. Annual time-series data that spanned 1978–2018 for Ghana were used. The results reveal that public debt has no causal relationship with GDP in the short-run but there is unidirectional Granger causality running from public debt to GDP in the long run. Investment spending was found to have negative bi-directional causal relationship with GDP in the short-run but they have a positive bi-directional causal relationship in the long run. Conversely, no short-run causal relationship exists between government consumption expenditure and GDP but long-run Granger causality runs from government consumption expenditure to GDP.

Saungweme & Odhiambo (2021) investigates the debt-growth nexus by testing both the impact of aggregate public debt on economic growth and the relative impact of domestic and foreign public debt on economic growth using South Africa as the case study from 1970 to 2017. Based on the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) technique, the findings reveal that the impact of aggregated public debt on economic growth in South Africa is statistically significant and negative, both in the short run and in the long run. The results further reveal that domestic public debt and economic growth have a statistically significant and positive relationship in the short run only.

Abdulmumin (2022) employed secondary data over a period of 33 years from 1987 to 2020. The study employed the Autoregressive distributive lag (ARDL). The result of the study revealed that external debt is a positive determinant of economic growth in Nigeria. The study also revealed that domestic debt is a negative significant determinant of economic growth and it concludes that public debt has significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. The study therefore recommends that government of Nigeria should make more use of external debt than domestic debt because of the low interest of external debt to domestic debt which will help in reducing the debt burden in the long-run.

Awadzie and colleagues (2022) used a threshold autoregressive model by employing time-series data for thirty-one years from 1990 to 2020. The data reveal that Ghana has a single public debt threshold value, implying that public debt and growth are not linear. The derived threshold regression model indicates a public debt threshold of 57%, above which the growth rate of GDP per capita is considerably retarded. In addition, below the threshold level, there is a statistically significant positive association between public debt and growth.

Erick and colleagues (2023) uses time series data for the period of 2002-2020 to establish the relationship between public debt and economic growth in Kenya. The study established a negative effect of public debt on economic growth. However, the relationship was insignificant for the period under study. The effect of external debt was also negative but not significant on changes in GDP; while its effect on inflation rates was positive but insignificant. Domestic debt had insignificant positive effects on changes in GDP while its effect on inflation was negative but insignificant as well. The insignificant effect of domestic debt could be in part attributed to the underdeveloped capital markets in the Kenyan economy. From the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that public debt should be the last resort to public finance as it depicted negative effects on economic growth and additionally, Kenya should pursue comprehensive debt relief measures.

Hassan and colleagues (2023) aimed at analyzing the effect of public debt on economic growth in Kenya. The study used time series data for the period 1990 to 2019. The data was analyzed through the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression technique. The findings indicated that domestic debt had an insignificant negative effect on Kenyan economy while external debt has insignificant positive effect. The study concluded that internal debt has deleterious while external debt has positive effect on growth.

Alshaib and colleagues (2023) examines the association between fiscal sustainability indicators and Egypt's economic growth. They aimed to analyze the dynamic relationship between fiscal sustainability indicators and economic growth in Egypt. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach and unrestricted error correction model were applied to annual data from 1980 to 2018. A dynamic link was found between fiscal sustainability indicators and economic growth. Government expenditure and external debt significantly impacted economic expansion in the long term, while government revenue did not. Fiscal sustainability, measured by growth in total government expenses, external debt obligations, and revenue, significantly influences Egypt's economic growth.

Nyabakora (2023) examines the effect of public debt on the economic growth of Tanzania from 2009 to 2019. The study employs least squares methods to examine the relationship between variables of interest. The results revealed that external debt and private consumption are significant and positively affect economic growth. However, domestic debt has a negative, insignificant effect on economic growth. This means that governments have to take on more external debt than domestic debt due to the fact that borrowing internally can disturb private consumption. This is due to the fact that private consumption has a positive impact on economic growth. When the government borrows internally, it demonetizes the economy, which can slow economic growth.

Siyang (2024) used data obtained from different countries in examining impact of public debt on growth such as Brazil, Malaysia, South Africa, Thailand and Turkey. Firstly, the study analyzes the trends of public debts across these five countries. From the analysis, it could be realized that the level of government debt increased across all the countries. Moreover, the study also used a vector error correction model (VECM) methodology along with an impulse response function (IRF) to account for the country-wise impact of public debt on economic growth. The results showed that there is a negative impact on the economic growth of Brazil, Malaysia, Thailand, Turkey and South Africa. Furthermore, the study also accounts for the impact of fiscal policies on the debt management structure of the specified countries.

Taylor & Lokina (2024) examines the dynamic relationship between public debt and economic growth in Tanzania, focusing on causal links between the two variables and exploring potential debt thresholds. Using quarterly time series data from March 2005 to June 2022, they employ individual unit root and Johansen's cointegration tests to establish long-term relationships. The Vector Error Correction Model was estimated and the Granger causality test was performed. Findings of the study reveal a significant positive long-term relationship between the two variables, with the direction of causality running from economic growth to domestic debt. Notably, the positive impact of domestic debt is pronounced when the domestic debt-to-GDP ratio falls between 31.3% and 35.2%. Beyond this threshold, the established relationship becomes statistically insignificant. The paper advocates leveraging debt financing to support productive investments for long-term economic growth.

Data and Methodology

Data

The variables of interest selected in this study based on the availability and reliability of data includes; External Debts (ED), Domestic Debts (DD), External Debt Services (DS), and real GDP. The data were obtained from Tanzania National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and International Financial Statistics (IFS) Data Stream published by International Monetary Fund (IMF). The study use quantitative research design in which time series data are being used over a period of 1990 to 2023, the period has been chosen because of existence of policy changes particularly following new regime and adoption of different structural adjustment programmes.

Econometric Model

In order to analyze the impact of public debt on economic growth in Tanzania the following general function is being applied:

$$GDP = (ED, DD, DS) \tag{1}$$

Where GDP is being measured in real terms, ED is external debts, DD is domestic debts, and DS is external debt services. From literature point of view, public debt could have negative impact, positive impact or non-linear relationship with economic growth. The implication is that regression coefficients could assume any value positive or negative. Based on this explanation the model in this study is specified as;

$$GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ED_t + \beta_2 DD_t + \beta_3 DS_t + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots Eq \tag{2}$$

$$\beta_0 \neq 0, \beta_1 \neq 0, \beta_2 \neq 0, \beta_3 \neq 0$$

This paper employ a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), this approach is simply an extension of the Granger Causality test and which goes beyond the analysis of bivariate framework. Granger causality in principle separates cause and effect in order to determine which the cause is and which the effect is (Granger & Newbold, 1974). The VEC equation contains lagged values of all the variables in the system. The key objective of the analysis is to provide good statistical representation of the past interaction among the chosen variables. Since the VEC involves series of equations, it is assumed that each equation contains *K* lagged values as such the equation could be estimated using the OLS approach. Based on the specification in Eq(2) above, VEC models in this paper is presented as:

$$GDP_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{1j} ED_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{2j} DD_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{3j} DS_{t-1} + \beta_4 EC_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t}$$

$$ED_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{1j} GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{2j} DD_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{3j} DS_{t-1} + \beta_4 EC_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{2t}$$

$$DD_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{1j} GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{2j} ED_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{3j} DS_{t-1} + \beta_4 EC_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{3t}$$

$$DS_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{1j} GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{2j} ED_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_{3j} DD_{t-1} + \beta_4 EC_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{4t}$$

From the given series of equations, EC_{t-1} is error-correction term lagged one period. The coefficient of error term is normally expected to have a negative sign and measures speed of adjustment. The estimated ε_s are the error terms and also known as impulse or shocks elements. A clear distinction between causality and correlation is being provided in the study as the impulse responds function in the system of equations.

Results and Discussions

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity refers to “the presence or occurrence of a perfect, or exact, linear relationship among some or all explanatory variables in a regression model” (Sim, 1980). In this paper, presence of Multicollinearity was tested using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The rule of thumb is that if obtained VIF is less than 3 it indicates that there is no Multicollinearity among explanatory variables while, a VIF of more than 10 it indicates presence of Multicollinearity problem. Obtained VIF for all the independent variables were found to be less than 10 to support the proposition Multicollinearity problem does not exist. The VIF test results are being presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Multicollinearity Test Results

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
External Debts Services	1.15	0.870871
Domestic Debt	1.14	0.874463
External Debts	1.01	0.991478
Mean VIF	1.10	

Source: Author's Computation

The Unit Root Test

Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (ADF) was used in this study to test for stationarity of series. Based on the results of the stationarity tests at level it can be concluded that all of the variables do not have a unit root. Since the p value for all variables found to be less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is being rejected that means variables are stationary (Dickey-Fuller, 1981). The ADF test results are being presented in Table 2 variables at levels suggests that at 5% level of significance the null hypothesis is being rejected and hence spurious regression results can be avoided since variables are stationary.

Table 2. Unit Root Test Results at Levels

Variables	ADF-statistic	Critical Values
Real GDP	-1.405(0.021)	1% = -2.467
		5% = -1.701
		10% = -1.313
External Debts	-1.468(0.032)	1% = -2.457
		5% = -1.697
		10% = -1.310
External Debts Services	-2.374(0.0126)	1% = -2.479
		5% = -1.706
		10% = -1.315
Domestic Debt	-1.716(0.019)	1% = -2.457
		5% = -1.697
		10% = -1.310

Source: Author's Computation

Cointegration Test

Following the confirmation that all series included in the analysis are integrated at level, the next step is to test for the existence of a cointegration relationship among the variable using the Johansen-Juselius to see if long-run relationship among variables exists. The cointegration test results for all variables in the paper are reported in the Table 3. Test results suggest that there are two cointegrating equations in the series, since obtained trace statistics are less than critical values at 5% level of significance and two lags were found. Trace statistics is used to test null hypothesis that rank is zero against alternative hypothesis that rank is positive.

Table 3. Johansen Cointegration Test Results for GDP and ED

Maximum Rank	Parms	LL	Eingen Value	Trace Statistics	5% Critical Value
0	20	-2292.06		31.10	47.21
1	23	-2281.99	0.4780	10.96	29.68
2	35	-2277.52	0.2508	2.01	15.41
3	32	-2276.51	0.0628	0.00	3.76
4	34	-2276.59	0.0000		

Note: NB: Number of observations 34, number of lags 2.

Estimation of Long-Run Relationship

Next step after establishing that the residual of the regression as provided in equation two (2) is stationary, and also the variables are cointegrated as such the regression output at levels are not spurious and long-run relationship can be estimated (Engle & Granger, 1987). The estimation results obtained representing long-run relationship amongst the selected variables is presented in Table 4. External debts (ED) found with a negative sign (-0.0401) and statistically significant at one percent level which means external debt has negative effect on growth in Tanzania during the sampled period. The implication of the finding is that one unit increase in external debts decreases real GDP by 0.040 times. Similarly, External debt services (DS) found with negative sign (-0.0181) and statistically significant at five percent level. Domestic debts (DD) and real GDP were found to be positive related (0.0011) and statistically significant at one percent level. This implies that one percent increase in domestic debts of the country increases real GDP by 0.1 percent. These variables in the model generally explained the total changes of the real GDP by 89 per cent according to adjusted R-squared obtained and the rest of the percentage is being explained by other variables which are not included in this model.

Table 4. Long-Run Coefficient Estimation Results

Source	SS	DF	MS	Number of observations = 34		
Model	82.5990	27.5330	27.5330	F(3, 9) = 229.79		
Residual	3.4747	0.1198	0.1198	Prob > F = 0.0000		
				R-Squared = 0.9096		
				Adj. R-Squared = 0.8855		
				Root MSE = 0.3461		
Real GDP	COEFF.	STD. ERR	t statistic	P > [t]	[95% Confid. interval]	
ED	-0.0410*	0.1189	-2.90	0.0070	-1.3790	-0.2389
DS	-0.0181**	0.0463	-2.56	0.0160	-0.6320	-0.0710
DD	0.0011*	0.0046	4.22	0.0000	3.6096	6.0007
CONS	-0.1983*	0.9799	-8.55	0.0000	-84.5191	-51.8778

Note: NB: * and ** statistically significance at 1% and 5% respectfully.

Estimation of the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)

VECM **approach** resembles simultaneous-equation modeling in that several dependent variables are being considered together. However, each dependent variable is explained by its lagged values and the lagged values of all other independent variables in the model; usually, there are no independent variables in the model. Error Correction Model (ECM) is also used to bridge both short-run and long-run relationship within the context of a single equation (Sims, 1980). Before estimation of the specified regression model, the optimal lag length of each variable in the model have to be determined in order to ensure that the model is well specified. The Schwartz Bayesian Information Criterion (SBIC), Hannan Quinn Information Criterion (HQIC), Final Prediction Error (FPE) and the Akaike Information criterion (AIC) were used in this study in order to determine the optimal lag length. Ultimately, the optimal lag length were selected basing on which lag was mostly selected by four specified criteria. Table 5 below summarizes test results of lag selection criteria.

Table 5. Optimal Lag Selection Test Results

Variables	Lags	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBIC
Real GDP	2	0.0214	-1.0082	-0.9787	-0.9139
ED	1	0.0247	-0.8648	-0.8352	-0.7705
DS	1	25.7448	6.0859	6.1154	6.1802
DD	2	0.0003	-5.4472	-5.3882	-5.2586

Source: Author's Computation

The estimation results of VEC model when lagged in one period, and error correction term (ECT) is included for every variable is presented in Table 6. As can be seen from ΔGDP equation in Table 6, real GDP has an insignificant negative effect on ΔGDP . However, from ΔED equation, DD is having a positive effect on real GDP which is statistically significant at five percent level. It can also be observed from the ΔGDP equation that the one year lagged of external debt services (DS) has an insignificant negative impact on real GDP. Hence, current year external debt services have no significant impact on the previous values of real GDP. This is in line with the study of Mohamed (2018), Sharaf (2021) and Saungwene & Odhiambo (2018). The coefficient of domestic debts (DD) shows that one year lagged values of domestic debts positively influence current value of real GDP in Tanzania. This implies that for economy to grow increase in the current year, amount domestic debts are acquire and put into production of goods and services within the country in the previous period should increase. This is similar to the findings of the study of Christabell (2013), Precious (2015) and Matthew & Mordecai (2016).

Table 6. Vector Error Correction Model Test Results

ΔPI	Coefficients	Std. Error	Z	P > [Z]	[95% Conf. Interval]	
EC_{t-1}	-0.0112	0.0173	-1.55	0.122	-0.0731	0.0086
GDP_{t-1}	-0.1030	0.2333	-0.44	0.659	-0.5602	0.3542
ΔED_{t-1}	-0.3705	0.2477	-1.50	0.135	-0.8559	0.1149
ΔDS_{t-1}	-0.0035	0.0062	-0.57	0.570	-0.0158	0.0087
ΔDD_{t-1}	0.4465	1.2881	0.35	0.729	-2.0783	2.9713
Constant	0.1256	0.0843	1.49	0.136	-0.0396	0.2908
ΔED	Coefficients	Std. Error	Z	P > [Z]	[95% Conf. Interval]	
EC_{t-1}	-0.0221	0.0444	-2.01	0.044	-0.7991	-0.0009
GDP_{t-1}	-0.1427	0.2253	-0.63	0.527	-0.5844	0.2989
ΔED_{t-1}	0.0166	0.2392	0.07	0.945	-0.4524	0.4855
ΔDS_{t-1}	0.0091	0.0060	1.51	0.131	-0.0027	0.0208
ΔDD_{t-1}	2.4897	1.2444	2.00	0.045	0.0508	4.9286
Constant	-0.0919	0.0814	-1.13	0.259	-2.2516	0.0676
ΔDS	Coefficients	Std. Error	Z	P > [Z]	[95% Conf. Interval]	
EC_{t-1}	-1.2310	2.6589	-2.16	0.031	-3.3146	-0.1615
GDP_{t-1}	-2.0385	9.0046	-0.23	0.821	-19.6872	15.6103
ΔED_{t-1}	5.3214	9.5603	0.56	0.578	-13.4163	24.0592
ΔDS_{t-1}	0.2092	0.2404	0.87	0.384	-0.2604	24.0592
ΔDD_{t-1}	-64.4545	49.7283	-1.30	0.195	-161.4114	0.6804
Constant	-0.0002	3.2538	-0.00	0.030	-6.3776	33.0025
ΔDD	Coefficients	Std. Error	Z	P > [Z]	[95% Conf. Interval]	
EC_{t-1}	0.0013	0.0033	0.40	0.691	-0.0052	0.0079
GDP_{t-1}	-0.0125	0.0373	-0.34	0.737	-0.0857	0.0606
ΔED_{t-1}	0.0435	0.0396	1.10	0.272	-0.0341	0.1212
ΔDS_{t-1}	0.0008	0.0009	0.79	0.428	-0.0011	0.0027
ΔDD_{t-1}	0.2849	0.2060	1.38	0.167	-0.1189	0.6886
Constant	0.1385	0.3933	2.84	0.005	0.0118	0.0647

Source: Author's Computation

The Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) Test for Structural Break

The CUSUM test is a “test for structural breaks in the coefficients (parameter stability) of a linear regression model” (Brown *et al.*, (1975). Statistical inference performed is based on a sequence of sums, or sums of squares, of recursive residuals (standardized one-step-ahead forecast errors) computed iteratively from nested subsamples of the data under consideration. The CUSUM test bases its result on whether the time-series data set abruptly changes in ways not forecasted by the formulated model of the

study. Said more technically, it tests for structural breaks in the residuals and test results are being presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Cumulative Sum Test Results for Parameter Stability

Sample: 1990 – 2023 H0: No structural break		Number of obs = 34		
	Test	Critical value		
Type	Statistic	1%	5%	10%
Recursive	3.0381	0.0330	0.0461	0.0689

Source: Author's Computation

It can be seen from obtained result the null hypothesis of no structural break at 5 percent level of statistical significance is being accepted. Selected sample of the study it does track the data over time, and hence obtained regression results is not bias.

Conclusion

This paper empirically examines the impact of Tanzania's public debt on economic growth over a period of 1990 to 2023. Toward achieving this objective, a VECM approach and Johansen cointegration analysis were employed to test for causal relationships between the variables of interest including Real GDP, domestic and external debt, and external debt services. Being consistent with the Keynesian theory, the domestic debt was found to positively affects real output and lasts for one year. However, the empirical results revealed a negative and significant long-run relationship between real GDP and external debts, as well as real GDP and external debt services, indicating that external debts and it is services impair economic growth in Tanzania. Empirical evidence also support the crowding-out effect caused by external and not domestic debt.

Based on obtained empirical evidence, this paper recommends to the government to pursue appropriate strategies and policies on public debt with the intention of improving economic growth and development. Furthermore, the study cautions the country against growing external debt to finance its increasing expenditure needs as this was found to have adverse effects on economic growth in the long run. The implication of the obtained empirical results is that the government should be able to design policies to effectively utilize and manage the public debt to increase productive activities and, hence, promote sustainable economic growth and improvement of social welfare.

There are various ways in which this research could be extended by interested academicians in public debts-economic growth nexus. First, examining Tanzania's public debt threshold value is necessary because of the lack of consistency results in the literature. Further investigation on Tanzania's debt threshold value would be interesting in ensuring that it is within the suggested threshold values. Second, despite taking requisite measures in this study to reduce misspecification error and improve the predictive power of the model, other important variables can also be included, such as, but not limited to, public investment, private investment and institutional framework within which country operate. Third, some theoretical arguments in the literature suggest that the impact of public debt on economic growth could be of a nonlinear nature. Hence, it would be worthwhile for further research to test the existence of nonlinear relationships between public debt and economic growth and thus validate the hypothesis of a "Public Debt Laffer curve" and ascertain the respective threshold points in Tanzania. Last, while investigating the effect of public debt on both poverty level and labor costs is beyond the scope of this research, it is important for further studies on the subject to move in this direction. This is significant as high level of poverty and costs of labor in developing countries like Tanzania can potentially reduce growth and lead to macroeconomic instability.

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